

Physiological adaptations of *Nannochloropsis* sp., under elevated pCO₂ conditions: Evidence from controlled culture experiments

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Abstract: Understanding the nutrient assimilation and carbon fixation in microalgae found crucial for analysing the role in marine productivity and potential applications in carbon sequestration. In the present study, controlled culture experiments under varying pCO₂ conditions to assess nutrient assimilation, pigment synthesis and carbon fixation. The secondary peak in silicate, 189.04 μM (Day 9 - 11) likely attributed to the frustule dissolution from dead cells in the medium. Carbon fixation by *Nannochloropsis* sp. ranged between 8.64 and 10.78 g L⁻¹ d⁻¹, lower than reported in previous studies, reflecting the influence of culture conditions and sensitivity to acidification. Elevated CO₂ was found to hinder RuBisCO activity and reduce bicarbonate availability, thereby limiting fixation efficiency. Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong negative relationships between chlorophyll-a and both inorganic phosphate (-0.77) and nitrate (-0.52), indicating their critical role in pigment production. A positive correlation between nitrate, nitrite, and IP suggested consistent nutrient uptake patterns throughout the culture. Collectively, the observed results highlight the adaptations of *Nannochloropsis* sp. under stress conditions, highlighting the importance of nutrient equilibrium and optimal carbonate chemistry for sustaining productivity.

Keywords: *Nannochloropsis* sp., pCO₂, microalgae culture, Carbon fixation, Nutrient assimilation

I. Introduction

The global warming driven by Carbon-di-oxide (CO₂) emissions become a major concern across scientific, environmental and economic sectors. The CO₂ emissions were considered long term as it retained for 50-200 years. Consequently, regulating and reducing emissions of gases such as CO₂ become prioritized (Cheah et al., 2015). The increasing CO₂ emissions in the atmosphere controlled by several CO₂ removal factors such as physio-chemical absorption, transportation to deeper oceans and biological fixation are well developed (Kumar et al., 2011). Moreover, in accordance with Global CCS Technology Research Centre report (2016), reported that CO₂ capture mechanisms found efficient but the relative energy consumption found to be a major problem (Xu et al., 2019).

Among the CO₂ capture mechanisms, biological fixation gained attention due to the contribution of biomass via photosynthesis process. Specifically, microalgae fixation is economically feasible, eco-friendly and sustainable CO₂ sequestration technology and also microalgae gained more attraction due to its unique features. Microalgae known for its high growth rate intensity and CO₂ fixation capacity than the terrestrial photoautotrophs. Generally, microalgae are photoautotrophs, as it converts the energy and adaption to environmental conditions (Singh and Ahluwalia, 2013). Algae contribute about 50% of the earth's photosynthesis process (Singh and Singh, 2014).

The anthropogenic CO₂ emission from power plants contribute about 7% of global CO₂ emissions (Morais and Costa, 2007). It is vital to select the candidate microalgae species to execute and efficient and

economical CO₂ fixation process based on the growth rate, tolerance, sequestration capacity and withstand with wide range of environmental factors. The tolerance towards different pCO₂ conditions determined by capacity of the species (Singh and Ahluwalia, 2013; Ho et al., 2011).

Several CO₂ tolerance studies carried out with this species, reported that *Nannochloropsis* sp. exhibited a higher growth rate under the CO₂ emissions of 5 -50% of CO₂ (Sakai et al, 1995; Murakami and Ikenouchi., 1997; Tang et al., 2011; Solovchenko and Khozin-Goldberg, 2013). In contrast, several studies suggest, the growth and photosynthetic activity inhibited under different CO₂ conditions (Silva and Pirt, 1984; Lee and Tay, 1991). Therefore, *Chlorella* sp., likely varying its physiological adaptations toward enhanced CO₂ conditions. In the present study, *Nannochloropsis* sp. cultured under different pCO₂ conditions to estimate the CO₂ fixation and physiological responses throughout the culture.

II. Materials and methods

2.1 Algae culture

In the *Nannochloropsis* sp., algal experiment study, the culture were maintained using Guillard's F/2 = Si medium (Guillard, 1975) following a batch culture method. The cultures were maintained in constant room temperature of 25°C under 12hr light/ 12hr dark photoperiod (Lananan et al., 2013). The culture medium was carried out in 5L Erlenmeyer flasks, with an inoculum to sterilized seawater ratio of 2.5:10. The flask openings were sealed with steril, non-absorbent cotton wool to prevent contamination.

2.2 Experimental setup

The experiment was designed to understand the physiological adaptations under different pCO₂ conditions. According to IPCC (2007) projections, further increases in pCO₂ will be accompanied by decline in ocean pH level. In line with these projections, the present study-maintained target conditions by regulating pH levels rather than maintaining it via pCO₂ levels. Totally four treatments were applied: control, pH 7.1, 7.3 and 7.5. The desired pH was manually infusing CO₂ gas from cylinder to the cultures until the desired pH reached. Cell growth and proliferation were monitored using hemacytometer. From each treatment, 125ml of samples drawn to estimate the nutrient uptake and chl-a levels (Strickland and Parsons, 1972 & Grashoff et al, 2009). The nutrients such as Ammonia, Nitrate, Nitrite, Silicate, Inorganic Phosphate (IP). A summary of IPCC projections presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. IPCC (2007) report on future ocean scenarios: pH and pCO₂

Oceanic pH	Oceanic pCO ₂ (µatm)
pH 7.5	~950 – 1000+
pH 7.3	~1200 – 1400
pH 7.1	~1800 – 2000

2.3 CO₂ fixation rate

The CO₂ fixation rate was determined according to the standard protocols of Park *et al.*, (2021). This calculation performed on the last sampling day of the culture.

$$RC = CC \cdot P \cdot MCO_2/MC$$

Eq (1)

Where, CC denotes the carbon fraction of the produced biomass, CC value obtained after the CHNS analysis of culture sample. P refers to the biomass productivity as said earlier and MCO₂/MC represent the ratio of molecular weight of Carbon dioxide to Carbon (Park *et al.*, 2021).

III. Results and discussion

3.1 Nutrient and chl-a variations under different pCO₂ conditions

Nutrient limitation of phytoplankton has been reported extensively in different culture approach. Among the nutrients, ammonia, nitrate, silicate and IP plays a pivotal role in limiting biological productivity (Gruber, 2004). Carbon (C): Nitrogen (N): Phosphorous (P) determined on the phytoplankton groups (Quigg *et al.*, 2003; Klausmeier *et al.*, 2004) and also in relation to nutrient, photo and physiological adaptations (Laws and Bannister, 1980; Healey, 1985; Flynn, 2001). Nitrate addition was strongly promoted phytoplankton bloom reported by the nutrient enrichment experiment in the north-western Indian Ocean (Takeda *et al.*, 1995) Nitrate and IP in central Indian Ocean (Tang *et al.*, 2009) and Nitrate, IP and Silicate in yellow sea (Zou *et al.*, 2001). In the present study, variations in nutrient assimilation of *Nannochloropsis* sp., microalgae culture maintained under different pCO₂ conditions via pH 7.1, 7.3 and 7.5. Nutrients such as Ammonia, IP, Silicate, Nitrite, Nitrate and Chl-a were tracked throughout the culture.

3.2 Ammonia

In control sample, the minimum concentration observed 0.24 (Day1) and maximum concentration observed 2.62 μM (Day 11). In pH 7.1, the minimum and maximum concentration observed are 0.243 μM (Day 3) and 2.453 μM (Day 13). In pH 7.3, ammonia concentration ranged between 0.201 μM (Day 1) and 2.55 μM (Day 13). In pH 7.5 sample, the ammonia concentration varied between 0.25 μM (Day 1) and 2.25 μM (Day 11). The peak ammonia levels exhibited during death phase (Day 11-13), could be due to the mortality of species present in the culture medium. The ammonia concentration during the culture period represented in figure.1. Ammonia nitrogen (NH₃-N) plays a major role in supporting microalgae growth. However, increase in Ammonia concentration leads to the ammonia toxicity to microalgae and affects the microalgal growth (He *et al.*, 2013, Tan *et al.*, 2016, Zheng *et al.*, 2019). Increased ammonia concentration also inhibits chl-a productions (Ayre *et al.*, 2017) by ammonia binding to Mn complex.

Figure.1 Ammonia concentration throughout the culture period

3.3 Silicate

In control sample, the minimum and maximum silicate concentration observed in 15.342 μM (Day 13) and 40.35 μM (Day 7). In pH 7.1, the silicate concentration ranged from 14.875 μM (Day 13) to 49.587 μM (Day 9). In pH 7.2, silicate concentration varied between 8.68 μM (Day 7) and 62.61 μM (Day 9). In pH 7.5, lowest concentration observed in 9.044 μM (Day 7) and the peak concentration observation observed in 69.036 μM (Day 9). Silicate concentration peaked on the days of 9 and 11, the resuspension of silicate frustules from the cell walls of dead microalgae species in the medium. The silicate patterns shown in figure.3. The factors including light intensity, temperature and nutrient availability (Phosphorous and Nitrogen) significantly impact the silicate assimilation in microalgae. In nutrient rich environment, silicate consumption occurs rapidly to support cell proliferation (Martin-Jézéquel *et al.*, 2000). The observed secondary silicate concentration peak (189.035 μM) on day 9 to 11, indicates the cell permeability. This process leads to the release of consumed silicate back to the medium and the correlation analysis also exhibited positive correlation with ammonia (Martin-Jézéquel, 2000).

Figure.3 Silicate concentration throughout the culture period

3.4 Nitrite, Nitrate and IP

In control sample, the minimum and maximum nitrite concentration observed are 2.106 μM (Day 1) and 11.77 μM (Day 5). In sample pH7.1, the Nitrite concentration ranged from 0.59 μM (Day 11) to 18.87 μM (Day 5). In pH7.3, the peak nitrite concentration observed in 16.03 μM (Day 3) and minimum concentration observed in 0.65 μM (Day 11). In pH7.5 sample, nitrite concentration varied between 0.97 μM (Day 11) and 14.63 μM (Day 3). The Nitrite assimilation pattern during the culture shown in figure. 3(a). In sample control, the peak nitrate concentration exhibited in 41.84 μM (Day 1) and the minimum concentration observed in 2.76 μM (Day 13). In pH7.1, nitrate concentration ranged between 3.02 μM (Day 13) and 42.382 μM (Day 1). In pH7.3, nitrate levels stretched from 1.908 μM (Day 13) to 41.657 μM (Day 1). In pH7.5, maximum concentration observed in 40.929 μM (Day 1) and the minimum concentration observed in 3.503 μM (Day 7). The Nitrate levels during the culture demonstrated in figure.3(b). In control sample, the minimum and maximum IP varied between 0.024 μM (Day 7) and 22.306 μM (Day 1). In pH 7.1, IP concentration ranged from 0.113 μM (Day 7) to 21.457 μM (Day 1). In pH 7.3 sample, the minimum IP concentration observed in 0.131 μM (Day 11) and the maximum IP concentration observed in 23.172 μM (Day 1). In pH 7.5, the peak IP concentration observed in 23.34 μM (Day 1) and the minimum IP concentration observed in 0.113 μM (Day 9), demonstrated in Fig.3 (c). Throughout this culture study, IP concentration found to be higher in the initial stages of culture, due to the presence IP levels in the culture medium, meanwhile a low concentration noted during growth phase (Day 7-9) attributed to the assimilation of IP by microalgae for its growth and proliferation. The IP uptake pattern during the culture period represented in figure.6. The observed declining trends in Nitrate (30.02-12.64 μM) and phosphate (1.98 – 0.13 μM) during the day 7 to 9 (growth phase) attributed to the consumption of these nutrients by microalgae and thus results with the enhancement of chl-*a* (181.63 to 88.86 $\mu\text{g/L}$). Thus,foundevidentthatNitrate and Phosphate boosts the microalgae production. The observed result aligns with the findings of Arrora et al, (2016), states that presence of Phosphorous content in growth media aids the uptake of Nitrate, energy transfer, signal transduction and photosynthetic respiration.

Figure.5 Nitrate concentration throughout the culture period

3.5 Chl-a

In control sample, the minimum and maximum chl-a concentration observed in 2.016 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 1) and 102.69 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 11). In pH7.1, the chl-a concentration stretched from 0.19 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 1) to 101.48 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 5). In sample pH7.3, peak chl level observed in 65.08 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 7) and minimum chl-a level in 1.34 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 3). In pH7.5, the chl-a levels varied from 0.305 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Day 3) to 83.350 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (day 7). The chl-a levels were presented in figure.4. During culture after day 9, Chl-a levels varied between 181.63 and 88.86 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The decreased chl-a levels due to the increased cell densities, inhibits the light penetration in algal culture. The increased cell densities inhibit the light penetration results with the reduction of microalgae reduction. This observation found consistent with the findings of Gladue et al, (1994) and Ratha et al, (2013), reported that increased cell densities block the efficient light penetration. As a result, final cell concentration generally remains low and yield 0.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure.4Chl-a levels throughout the culture period

3.6 CO₂ fixation by *Nannochloropsis* sp.

The carbon fixation results for *Nannochloropsis* sp. revealed with range of 8.64 to 10.78 g L⁻¹ d⁻¹ found low yield when compared with study reported by Cheng *et al.*, (2018), with the yield up to 31.9 g. L⁻¹. d⁻¹. This could be due to differences in culture methods compared with the present study. *Nannochloropsis* sp. revealed a carbon fixation result and found sensitive to the acidifying conditions, thus hinders the enzymatic activity specifically RuBisCO enzyme. RuBisCO enzyme mainly responsible for the carbon fixation (Raven *et al.*, 2011; Meng *et al.*, 2015) and also diminishes the bicarbonate ions availability considered vital for the carbon fixation (Gao and Campbell, 2014; Giordano *et al.*, 2005). Peak CO₂ conditions (10% to 20%) in flue gas supply sufficient carbon to induce the microalgal proliferation. Moreover, increased CO₂ leads to acidification leading to mortality so optimum conditions are necessary to maintain the culture (Aslam *et al.*, 2017). The CO₂ fixation result illustrated in figure.5.

Figure.5 represents the carbon fixation

3.7 Correlation matrices among the environmental variables

Throughout the culture period, the IP (-0.77) and Nitrate (-0.52) exhibited a strong negative correlation against chl-a, thus indicates the rapid assimilation of IP and Nitrate during growth phase leads to the contribution in algal biomass. A slight positive correlation (0.27) between Ammonia and chl-a, suggests that culture transitioning towards, during which ammonia level increases. Although, the chl-a found higher during the same pHase but weak correlation indicates that Ammonia level increases likely when the depletion of available nutrients. The strong positive correlation among Nitrate with Nitrite (0.81) and IP (0.80) and revealed the constant uptake rates throughout the study. The Pearson correlation results represented in figure.6. pCO₂ demonstrated a negative association with Nitrate (-0.3), IP (-0.25), Nitrite (-0.21) and chl-a (-0.08), whereas a weak positive correlation has been reported with ammonia (0.1) silicate (0.2).

The strong negative correlation between chl-a and both IP (-0.77) and Nitrate (-0.52), thus indicates the consumption of Nitrate and IP are vital for the chl-a pigment production. This observed result aligns with the findings of Rafay *et al.*, (2020), suggests that the observed assimilation of nitrate uptake attributed to the intracellular nitrogen storage in microalgal cells. Since the present study conducted as a batch culture, no continuous Nitrate supplied to the culture which resulted with the rapid uptake and leads to high chl-a levels. Dortch, (1982) states that, microalgae have adaptive mechanism that could be responsible for the *Nannochloropsis* sp. of the nutrient uptake including Nitrate and IP beyond the sufficient margin in anticipation of future nutrient depleting periods. The strong positive correlation found between Nitrate with Nitrite (0.81) and IP (0.80), suggests that uptake rates of these mentioned nutrients found consistent throughout the culture (Hu *et al.*, 2008).

Figure.6 Pearson correlation among environmental variables

3.8 PCA analysis

The eigen values for axis 1 and 2 are 3.04 and 1.16. Axes 1 and 2 account for a total variation of 60.9%. In axis 1, pCO₂ exhibits a negative correlation with factors such as chl-a (-0.39), Ammonia (-0.35) and Silicate (-0.20). Meanwhile in axis 2, pCO₂ demonstrated a strong positive correlation (0.6521) with silicate (0.406) and IP (0.21). The axes 1 and 2, revealed a total variance of 60.9%. In axis 1, pCO₂ exhibited a negative association with chl-a, Ammonia and Silicate, indicates that during death phase chl-a levels generally found higher simultaneously diminishes the CO₂ uptake process due to reduced activity leading to high pCO₂. Such a relationship is supported by Chiu *et al*, (2009) states that co-ordinated CO₂ fixation and nutrient uptake hindered with specific CO₂ conditions. In axis 2, pCO₂ exhibited a positive correlation with silicate possibly due to the resuspension of silicate during death phase.

Table: 2 PCA components *Nannochloropsis* sp.

<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp. Extracted Eigenvectors		
	Coefficients of PC1	Coefficients of PC2
pCO₂	-0.19954	0.65218
Chl-a	-0.38734	-0.45144
Ammonia	-0.34649	-0.239
Nitrate	0.51014	-0.08789
Nitrite	0.35484	-0.30867
IP	0.51251	0.21346
Silicate	-0.20317	0.40642

Figure.7 PCA plot of *Nannochloropsis* sp.

IV. Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that nutrient availability and CO₂ conditions strongly influence the growth and carbon fixation capacity of *Nannochloropsis* sp. The rapid assimilation of Nitrate, IP and silicate supported chl-a production. Meanwhile, reduced carbon fixation under high CO₂ conditions hindered by enzymatic and carbonate availability. Statistical analysis supports the close link between nutrient assimilation and pCO₂ dynamics, particularly during declining phase. Overall, the results highlight the sensitivity of microalgae to nutrient limitation and acidification, underscoring the need for balanced nutrient composition and stable carbonate chemistry to sustain productivity and leads to future application to the carbon management.

V. References

- Aslam, A., Thomas-Hall, S. R., Mughal, T. A., & Schenk, P. M. (2017). Selection and adaptation of microalgae to growth in 100% unfiltered coal-fired flue gas. *Bioresource technology*, 233, 271-283.
- Cheah, W. Y., Show, P. L., Chang, J. S., Ling, T. C., & Juan, J. C. (2015). Biosequestration of atmospheric CO₂ and flue gas-containing CO₂ by microalgae. *Bioresource technology*, 184, 190-201.
- Cheng, J., Yang, Z., Zhou, J., & Cen, K. (2018). Improving the CO₂ fixation rate by increasing flow rate of the flue gas from microalgae in a raceway pond. *Korean Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 35(2), 498-502.
- Chiu, S. Y., Kao, C. Y., Tsai, M. T., Ong, S. C., Chen, C. H., & Lin, C. S. (2009). Lipid accumulation and CO₂ utilization of *Nannochloropsis* *soculata* in response to CO₂ aeration. *Bioresource technology*, 100(2), 833-838.
- Dortch, Q. (1990). The interaction between ammonium and nitrate uptake in phytoplankton. *Marine ecology progress series*, 183-201.
- Flynn, K. J. (2001). A mechanistic model for describing dynamic multi-nutrient, light, temperature interactions in phytoplankton. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 23(9), 977-997.
- Gao, K., & Campbell, D. A. (2014). PhotoPhysiological responses of marine diatoms to elevated CO₂ and decreased pH: a review. *Functional Plant Biology*, 41(5), 449-459.
- Giordano, M., Beardall, J., & Raven, J. A. (2005). CO₂ concentrating mechanisms in algae: mechanisms, environmental modulation, and evolution. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.*, 56(1), 99-131.
- Grasshoff, K., Kremling, K., & Ehrhardt, M. (Eds.). (2009). *Methods of seawater analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gruber, N. (2004). The dynamics of the marine nitrogen cycle and its influence on atmospheric CO₂ variations. In *The ocean carbon cycle and climate* (pp. 97-148). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- Guillard, R. R. (1975, October). Culture of phytoplankton for feeding marine invertebrates. In *Culture of marine invertebrate animals: proceedings—1st conference on culture of marine invertebrate animals greenport* (pp. 29-60). Boston, MA: Springer US.
- Healey, F. P. (1985). Interacting effects of light and nutrient limitation on the growth rate of *Synechococcus linearis* (cyanophyceae) 1. *Journal of Phycology*, 21(1), 134-146.
- Ho, S. H., Chen, C. Y., Lee, D. J., & Chang, J. S. (2011). Perspectives on microalgal CO₂-emission mitigation systems—a review. *Biotechnology advances*, 29(2), 189-198.

14. Hu, Q., Sommerfeld, M., Jarvis, E., Ghirardi, M., Posewitz, M., Seibert, M., & Darzins, A. (2008). Microalgal triacylglycerols as feedstocks for biofuel production: perspectives and advances. *The plant journal*, 54(4), 621-639.
15. Klausmeier, C. A., Litchman, E., Daufresne, T., & Levin, S. A. (2004). Optimal nitrogen-to-phosphorus stoichiometry of phytoplankton. *Nature*, 429(6988), 171-174.
16. Kumar, K., Dasgupta, C. N., Nayak, B., Lindblad, P., & Das, D. (2011). Development of suitable photobioreactors for CO₂ sequestration addressing global warming using green algae and cyanobacteria. *Bioresour. Technol.*, 102(8), 4945-4953.
17. Lananan, F., Jusoh, A., Ali, N. A., Lam, S. S., & Endut, A. (2013). Effect of Conway Medium and f/2 Medium on the growth of six genera of South China Sea marine microalgae. *Bioresour. Technol.*, 141, 75-82.
18. Laws, E. A., & Bannister, T. T. (1980). Nutrient- and light-limited growth of *Thalassiosira fluviatilis* in continuous culture, with implications for phytoplankton growth in the ocean I. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 25(3), 457-473.
19. Lee, Y. K., & Tay, H. S. (1991). High CO₂ partial pressure depresses productivity and bioenergetic growth yield of *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* culture. *Journal of applied phycology*, 3(2), 95-101.
20. Martin-Jézéquel, V., Hildebrand, M., & Brzezinski, M. A. (2000). Silicon metabolism in diatoms: implications for growth. *Journal of Phycology*, 36(5), 821-840.
21. Meng, Y., Jiang, J., Wang, H., Cao, X., Xue, S., Yang, Q., & Wang, W. (2015). The characteristics of TAG and EPA accumulation in *Nannochloropsis oceanica* IMET1 under different nitrogen supply regimes. *Bioresour. Technol.*, 179, 483-489.
22. Morais, M. G.D., & Costa, J. A. V. (2007). Isolation and selection of microalgae from coal fired thermoelectric power plant for biofixation of carbon dioxide. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 48(7), 2169-2173.
23. Murakami, M., & Ikenouchi, M. (1997). The biological CO₂ fixation and utilization project by rite (2)—Screening and breeding of microalgae with high capability in fixing CO₂—. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 38, S493-S497.
24. Paasche, E. (1980). Silicon content of five marine plankton diatom species measured with a rapid filter method I. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 25(3), 474-480.
25. Pachauri, R. K., & Reisinger, A. (2007). IPCC fourth assessment report. *IPCC, Geneva, 2007*(673), 044023.
26. Park, J., Kumar, G., Bakonyi, P., Peter, J., Nemestóthy, N., Koter, S., ... & Kim, S. H. (2021). Comparative evaluation of CO₂ fixation of microalgae strains at various CO₂ aeration conditions. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*, 12(6), 2999-3007.
27. Quigg, A., Finkel, Z. V., Irwin, A. J., Rosenthal, Y., Ho, T. Y., Reinfelder, J. R., ... & Falkowski, P. G. (2003). The evolutionary inheritance of elemental stoichiometry in marine phytoplankton. *Nature*, 425(6955), 291-294.
28. Rafay, R., Uratani, J. M., Hernandez, H. H., & Rodríguez, J. (2020). Growth and nitrate uptake in *Nannochloropsis gaditana* and *Tetraselmis chuii* cultures grown in sequential batch reactors. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7, 77.
29. Raven, J. A., Giordano, M., Beardall, J., & Maberly, S. C. (2011). Algal and aquatic plant carbon concentrating mechanisms in relation to environmental change. *Photosynthesis Research*, 109(1), 281-296.
30. Raya, I., Anshar, A. M., Mayasari, E., Dwiyan, Z., & Asdar, M. (2016). *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Spirulina platensis*: Concentration of protein, Docosahexaenoic Acid *Chlorella* (DHA), Eicosapentaenoic Acid (EPA) and variation concentration of maltodextrin via microencapsulation method. *Int. J. Appl. Chem.*, 12, 539-548.
31. Sakai, N., Sakamoto, Y., Kishimoto, N., Chihara, M., & Karube, I. (1995). *Chlorella* strains from hot springs tolerant to high temperature and high CO₂. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 36(6-9), 693-696.
32. Silva, H. J., & Pirt, S. J. (1984). Carbon dioxide inhibition of photosynthetic growth of *Chlorella*. *Microbiology*, 130(11), 2833-2838.
33. Singh, S. P., & Singh, P. (2014). Effect of CO₂ concentration on algal growth: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 38, 172-179.
34. Singh, U. B., & Ahluwalia, A. S. (2013). Microalgae: a promising tool for carbon sequestration. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 18(1), 73-95.
35. Solovchenko, A., & Khozin-Goldberg, I. (2013). High-CO₂ tolerance in microalgae: possible mechanisms and implications for biotechnology and bioremediation. *Biotechnology Letters*, 35(11), 1745-1752.
36. Strickland, J. D. H., & Parsons, T. R. (1972). A practical handbook of seawater analysis.

37. Takeda, S., Kamatani, A., & Kawanobe, K. (1995). Effects of nitrogen and iron enrichments on phytoplankton communities in the northwestern Indian Ocean. *Marine Chemistry*, 50(1-4), 229-241.
38. Tang, D., Han, W., Li, P., Miao, X., & Zhong, J. (2011). CO₂ biofixation and fatty acid composition of *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* in response to different CO₂ levels. *Bioresource technology*, 102(3), 3071-3076.
39. Tang, D., Zhao, H., Satyanarayana, B., Zheng, G., Singh, R. P., Lv, J., & Yan, Z. (2009). Variations of chlorophyll-a in the northeastern Indian Ocean after the 2004 South Asian tsunami. *International journal of remote sensing*, 30(17), 4553-4565.
40. Xu, X., Gu, X., Wang, Z., Shatner, W., & Wang, Z. (2019). Progress, challenges and solutions of research on photosynthetic carbon sequestration efficiency of microalgae. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 110, 65-82.
41. Zou, L., Zhang, J., Pan, W. X., & Zhan, Y. P. (2001). In situ nutrient enrichment experiment in the Bohai and Yellow Sea. *Journal of plankton research*, 23(10), 1111-1119.

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